

SMS FINAL CONFERENCE REPORT

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Author(s)	Gundula Prokop
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CONTENT

1	BACKGROUND TO THIS DOCUMENT	1
1.1	Objectives and scope	1
1.2	Target audience of this report	1
2	CONFERENCE SET-UP.....	1
2.1	Organisation roles.....	1
2.2	Target audience	1
2.3	Conference venue.....	2
2.4	COVID19 precautions.....	2
2.5	Content to be communicated.....	2
2.6	Engagement	3
3	PARTICIPANTS.....	3
4	AGENDA	4
5	INFORMATIVE SESSIONS	5
5.1	Presentations.....	5
5.2	Graphic recording	8
6	INTERACTIVE SESSIONS.....	9
6.1	Interactive presentation of SMS project results	9
6.2	Panel discussion	9
6.3	Line-up	10
6.4	Vision journey workshop	11
6.5	Evaluation by participants	13
7	RESSOURCES	15
8	COMMUNICATION & DISSEMINATION.....	16
8.1	Before the conference	16
8.2	After the conference.....	16
9	CONCLUSIONS	17
10	ANNEX	18
10.1	Conference minutes.....	18

FIGURES

Fig. 1: Welcome Sketch	1
Fig. 2: Conference venue	2
Fig. 3: Proportion of online and in-situ participants.	3
Fig. 4: Participants of SMS final conference according to sectors.....	3
Fig. 5: Agenda of SMS final conference	4
Fig. 6: Presentation by N. Reeve (DG Research) “Introduction to EU missions”	5
Fig. 7: Presentation by O. Frizon Somogyi (DG AGRI) “A Soil Deal for Europe”	5
Fig. 8: Presentation P.A. Eulalio, (DG AGRI) “100 Living Labs and Lighthouses to lead the transition towards healthy soils by 2030”	6
Fig. 9: Presentation Marta De Los Rios White (ENOLL) “European Network of Living Labs” and J. Devis (AMS Institute) “The role of Living Labs in soil improvements”	6
Fig. 10: Presentation of the EJP Soil project by Claire Chenu (INRAE)	7
Fig. 11: Margrethe Balling Høstgaard, Aarhus University, “The PREPSOIL project 2022-2025: Preparing for the ‘Soil Deal for Europe’ Mission”	7
Fig. 12: Graphic recording – SMS final conference	8
Fig. 13: Presentation of SMS results.....	9
Fig. 14: Panel discussion at SMS final conference.....	10
Fig. 15: Line-up towards the soil mission objectives	10
Fig. 16: Results of the three vision journeys	12
Fig. 17: Evaluation results from the on-line survey	14
Fig. 18: SMS press text.....	16

TABLES

Table 1: Key roles of conference organisation	1
Table 2: External costs of SMS final conference.....	15

ABBREVIATIONS

CAP	Common Agricultural Programme of the European Commission
DoA	Description of Action of the Research Contract
DG	Directorate-General
EU	European Union
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
LL	Living Lab
LH	Lighthouse
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
SMS	Soil Mission Support
WP	Work package

1 BACKGROUND TO THIS DOCUMENT

1.1 Objectives and scope

The SMS final conference was held in Brussels on September 27th 2022 with the objective to inform on the EU soil research mission and how this mission is supported by results of the SMS project.

With this report we would like to share our knowledge gain with regard to organising a multi-stakeholder conference in times of COVID.

1.2 Target audience of this report

The key target group of this report are conference organisers in particular within the Horizon Europe Research programme. In this report we share our experience with regard to

- COVID secure planning,
- engagement of participants and use of innovative communication tools (conference design),
- dissemination and communication before and after the conference, and
- resources invested in conference planning.

2 CONFERENCE SET-UP

2.1 Organisation roles

The organisation of the SMS final conference started 10 months beforehand. Key roles were appointed throughout the planning process:

Table 1: Key roles of conference organisation

Role	Appointed person / organisation
Overall responsibility of organising the SMS final conference	Overall responsibility of organising the SMS final conference was given to the Austrian Environment Agency. The organisation of the conference was part of the DoA (WP 4 / task 4.3).
Conference manager	Katrin Stockhammer (Environment Agency Austria) was appointed as overall conference manager, being responsible for the selection of the venue, the invitations, the programme, the conference design and the procurement issues and GDPR.
Conference planning team	As of January 2022 a conference planning team was set up, meeting on a regular basis (approx. monthly).
Key moderator	Ms. Sakia Keestra (Wageningen University)
Supplementary moderators	Linda Maring (DELTARES), Katharina Helming (ZALF), Johannes Bender (BLE) and Antonio Bispo (INRAE).
Other roles	other roles, not further specified included minutes takers, a photographer, front desk registration etc..

2.2 Target audience

The key target audience of the conference can be summarised as actors dealing with the implementation of the EU soil mission. A detailed study of relevant actors was carried out in WP3 of the project (actor analysis) and resulted in the identification of more than 700 European actors from soil related sectors. Based on the results from the actor analysis a mailing list with more than 700 addresses was available and was used for sending out invitations to the SMS final conference.

Fig. 1: Welcome Sketch

2.3 Conference venue

The conference venue was selected according to the following criteria:

- State of the art conference technology with regard to sound, video and the option for online live-streaming.
- Easy to reach by public transport
- Ample space to host 80 participants
- Reasonable price

Three conference venues were pre-selected and visited beforehand. The nHow hotel was chosen as best candidate according to the above mentioned selection criteria (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2: Conference venue

2.4 COVID19 precautions

Conference planning started in January 2022, when COVID travel restrictions were still in place all over Europe and a prediction of the COVID situation in September 2022 was extremely difficult. For this reason, conference planning considered two scenarios:

- **Business as usual.** Planning of a “face to face” conference in Brussels with approximately 80 participants. In addition several COVID precautions were implemented at the venue:
 - Seating of participants around tables with plenty of space in order to avoid crowded situations
 - Provision of hand sanitiser in many places
 - Live-streaming of the morning session for those who have to cancel their participation on an adhoc basis and for additional online partners.
- **Back-up plan.** If COVID restrictions do not allow travelling to Brussels for at least some European countries, the conference should be held online. The decision deadline for this plan was set with August 15 2022.

2.5 Content to be communicated

Key objective of the conference was to inform on the EU soil mission and how it is supported by results of the SMS project. This was achieved by

- a general introduction to the EU missions and the soil mission in particular,
- a presentation of results generated by the SMS project,
- a panel discussion of key stakeholders,
- an interactive exercise with the conference participants reflecting on the feasibility of the soil mission, and
- a look into the future by presenting two ongoing projects related to the soil mission

2.6 Engagement

In order to achieve a maximum of engagement with the participants, both informative sessions and interactive sessions were organised.

- **Informative sessions** were carried out as describes in detail in chapter5.
- **Interactive sessions.** Interactive sessions as listed below were carried out in order to reach a maximum of engagement by the participants. All interactive sessions are described in detail in chapters 6.1 to 6.6.

3 PARTICIPANTS

Fig. 3: Proportion of online and in-situ participants.

Fig. 4: Participants of SMS final conference according to sectors

The conference was attended by in total 112 participants, of which 72 participants attended the whole conference in Brussels and 40 participants attended the meeting online. The morning session was streamed, whereas the afternoon session was reserved for “in-situ” attendants, due to the interactive character of the session (Fig. 3).

It has to be noted that 129 persons registered for an “in-situ participation” and only 72 persons actually showed up. Many registered participants opted for an on-line participation on a short notice, many of them without informing the organisers.

With regard to sectors it is evident that participants from research organisations were dominant with 50%, followed by policy makers with 15% and consulting firms with 11% (Fig. 4).

Regarding the geographical representation, participants represented 20 countries, of which 17 EU countries. Not represented EU member states appeared to be smaller countries (i.e. Luxemburg, Malta and Cyprus) and some eastern European countries (i.e. Bulgaria, Poland, Romania and Slovenia). However, representatives from all EU member states were invited to the conference.

4 AGENDA

A Soil Deal for Europe - European R&I Conference

September 27, 2022 | 9:00 – 16:30 CET

Hotel nhow Brussels Bloom, Rue Royale 250, 1210 Brussels, Belgium

PROGRAMME

08:30 – 09:00	Registration
09:00 – 09:45	<p>Opening (Moderator: <i>Johannes Bender</i>, Federal Office for Agriculture and Food, Germany)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Neville Reeve</i>, European Commission, DG for Research and Innovation • <i>Orsolya Frizon Somogyi</i>, European Commission, DG for Agriculture and Rural Development
09:45 – 10:30	<p>Results of the Soil Mission Support project (Moderator: <i>Saskia Keesstra</i>, WUR)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>SMS consortium members</i> (<i>Johannes Bender</i>, Federal Office for Agriculture and Food, Germany and <i>Katharina Helming</i>, Leibniz Centre for Agricultural Landscape Research, et al.): R&I needs, roadmap; ontology; living labs and lighthouses
10:30 – 11:20	<p>Towards Soil Health Living Labs and Lighthouses (Moderator: <i>Linda Maring</i>, Deltares)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Paola-Alejandra Eulalia</i>, European Commission, DG for Agriculture and Rural Development, "A Soil Deal for Europe: 100 living labs and lighthouses to lead the transition towards healthy soils by 2030" • <i>Marta De Los Rios White</i>, European Network of Living Labs (ENoLL) • <i>Juanita Devis</i>, Urban Living Lab, Amsterdam Institute for Advanced Metropolitan Solutions (AMS Institute), "The role of living labs in soil improvements"
11:20 – 11:40	Coffee Break
11:40 – 12:50	<p>Panel Discussion: Joining forces for achieving the soil mission – who is involved and what is required? (Moderator: <i>Katharina Helming</i>, Leibniz Centre for Agricultural Landscape Research)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Claudia Olazabal</i>, European Commission, DG for the Environment • <i>Orsolya Frizon Somogyi</i>, European Commission, DG for Agriculture and Rural Development • <i>Horst Herzog</i>, Network for Industrially Coordinated Sustainable Land Management in Europe (NICOLE) • <i>Liisa Pietola</i> (Finnish Innovation Fund Sitra)
12:50 – 13:50	Lunch Break
13:50 – 15:20	The future of European landscapes - Interactive exercise – vision journey (Moderator: <i>Katrin Stockhammer</i> , <i>Gundula Prokop</i> , Environment Agency Austria)
15:20 – 15:45	Coffee Break
15:45 – 16:20	<p>European projects on soil (Moderator: <i>Antonio Bispa</i>, National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and Environment, France)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Claire Chenu</i>, INRAE, EJP Soil project • <i>Margrethe Balling Høstgaard</i>, Aarhus University, "The PREPSOIL project 2022-2025: Preparing for the 'Soil Deal for Europe' Mission"
16:20 – 16:30	Reflections on the workshop and closing
16:30	After Workshop Coffee Lounge

Fig. 5: Agenda of SMS final conference

5 INFORMATIVE SESSIONS

Informative sessions were carried out via presentations and by means of graphic recording.

5.1 Presentations

Introduction to EU missions by Neville Reeve (DG for Research and Innovation) provided a general introduction of the concept of research missions as this is the case in the Horizon Europe programme. The idea was to create a common vision and bring citizens closer together to work jointly on societal innovations. Furthermore, major objectives were to have a clearer vision on the impact, to work cross-sectoral and to have a clear endpoint in mind. This was realised with the vision to achieve healthy soils by 2030. Finally, he highlighted the fact that there will be a review of all research missions in 2023 in order to find out what a mission approach requires. The review will be supported by OECD.

Fig. 6: Presentation by N. Reeve (DG Research) "Introduction to EU missions"

Introduction to the mission 'A Soil Deal for Europe' by Orsolya Frizon Somogyi (DG AGRI) stressed that soil health is a new approach and has to be seen as a long-term instrument. Society has to listen and adapt. Very important is the interaction between different actors, namely researchers, land users and policy makers. Soil health is not confined to agricultural topics, but also includes urban and industrial land uses and nature protection.

Our achievements so far...

- Two work programmes
- More than 250 events across Europe
- Preparing the ground: Prep-soil, project to engage with national communities and stakeholders to prepare the ground for the creation of living labs, project to work with municipalities and regions to improve soil health in their territories....
- International engagement

Fig. 7: Presentation by O. Frizon Somogyi (DG AGRI) "A Soil Deal for Europe"

Fig. 8: Presentation P.A. Eulalia, (DG AGRI) “100 Living Labs and Lighthouses to lead the transition towards healthy soils by 2030”

Fig. 9: Presentation Marta De Los Rios White (ENOLL) “European Network of Living Labs” and J. Devis (AMS Institute) “The role of Living Labs in soil improvements”

EJP Soil project, Claire Chenu (INRAE). EJP soil is a large European funding programme including 24 countries. Project funding is shared between the EU (50%) and Member States (50%). Key research topics are agricultural production, climate change adaption and mitigation and sustainable environment.

Fig. 10: Presentation of the EJP Soil project by Claire Chenu (INRAE)

Margrethe Balling Høstgaard, Aarhus University, “The PREPSOIL project 2022-2025: Preparing for the ‘Soil Deal for Europe’ Mission”. Key activities of the project are (i) to enhance stakeholder engagement in particular expansion of the national soil hub system, (ii) to evaluate soil needs in at least 19 European regions at the landscape level, (iii) to develop model business plans for Living Labs, (iv) and to establish a web portal with “best of” online material to inspire and connect citizens, in local official languages.

Fig. 11: Margrethe Balling Høstgaard, Aarhus University, “The PREPSOIL project 2022-2025: Preparing for the ‘Soil Deal for Europe’ Mission”

5.2 Graphic recording

Fig. 12: Graphic recording – SMS final conference

Graphic recording is a rather new workshop / conference tool. It is the skill of listening, synthesizing, and translating the spoken word into a drawing created in real-time. Most of the time, graphics are drawn on a large sheet of paper or artist board. However, with the shifting digital landscape, drawings are also commonly created on a tablet and projected on screens throughout the room.

The SMS team wanted to test this tool and find out how it works and if the results can later on be used. Another aspiration was the idea to produce illustrations that can be used without any copy right issues.

We chose the illustrator Rob van Barneveld from the Netherlands. His illustrations are scattered throughout this report. Both the SMS team and conference participants highly appreciated this tool.

The illustrations were immediately after the conference exhibited on the SMS website.

6 INTERACTIVE SESSIONS

6.1 Interactive presentation of SMS project results

Instead of presenting the results of the SMS project by individual and subsequent presentation, we thought it would be livelier to present the results in form of an “illustrated interview” and to have all key contributors on the stage answering the questions, while showing related slides. This session was moderated by Saskia Keestra who asked the questions. The interview was divided in four thematic blocks:

- SMS key points
- R&I gap analysis: stock and need assessment
- Living Labs and Lighthouses
- SMS research roadmap

Fig. 13: Presentation of SMS results

6.2 Panel discussion

The panel discussion named “Joining forces for achieving the soil mission” was moderated by Katharina Helming and panel guests were:

- Claudia Olazabal, European Commission, DG for the Environment
- Orsolya Frizon Somogyi, European Commission, DG for Agriculture and Rural Development
- Horst Herzog, Network for Industrially Coordinated Sustainable Land Management in Europe (NICOLE)
- Liisa Pietola (Finnish Innovation Fund Sitra)

Fig. 14: Panel discussion at SMS final conference

Key statements and knowledge gains from the panel discussion were:

- The Green Deal is seen as an economic growth agenda. One result is that the biodiversity strategy and the soil strategy are now connected.
- There should be a leverage effect from the Living Labs concept, in order to raise awareness, in society, industry, urban, agriculture. On top of that advisory services for soil health will also be incorporated in the CAP.
- The importance of ecosystem services was highlighted in the context of soil health, however, no conclusion or suggestion was given with regard to putting a price on eco-system services.
- The soil health law will be an evolving law, meaning that it will change over time and work needs to start as of 2023.

6.3 Line-up

In this session the question was raised “How likely is it that the Soil Mission Objectives will be achieved by 2030?” and all participants were asked to line up to this question. The left end of the line was reserved for sceptics and the right end for the enthusiasts.

As expected most participants positioned themselves in the middle. Interviews of randomly selected participants revealed that all participants believed in the scheme and in the objectives but most participants were very sceptic about the proposed time frame of the soil mission.

Fig. 15: Line-up towards the soil mission objectives

6.4 Vision journey workshop

An interactive exercise was organised in form of a vision journey. It had the intention to break the working and thinking along sectorial silos. Most people tend to think traditionally and follow existing patterns. On top of that, most experts are in their thinking confined to their sector. The vision journey had the ambition to overcome these barriers by bringing different experts together and by granting full freedom to creativity.

All participants were divided in groups and were asked to develop one of three “soil health scenarios”:

Scenario 1 / Soil Health Individual. You are the most soil conscious person and you are very influential, who are you?

- Dictator
- Part-time Soil Policy Entrepreneur and Farmer
- Sustainable Food Retailer
- Biology Teacher
- Astronaut (to look at earth from space and report)
- Multi-talent: Soil scientist, artist, farmer, Health - food advisor
- Citizen scientist, hobby farmer
- Soil artist
- Programme director
- Rockstar: ‘The Voice’. Bringing the Soil Mission into the world

Scenario 2 / Soil Health Technology. Describe the technology that would give soil health a real boost.

- Soil Health Monitoring
 - VR Glasses to explore soil like an earth-worm
 - ‘European soil pricing system’ based on satellite or aerial pictures: Obligation to pay a fee or remediate. Avoiding sealing is obligatory.
 - ‘Early worming system’: Based on smart fluorescent worms changing colours
 - ‘Soil Health Radar’
 - Tool to assess soil health in real time to help the decision making for agricultural practices. Farmers can use the results to communicate with the public and their buyers.
- Farming and soil cleaning
 - ‘Magnet’: A hovercraft harvester and tractor

- 'Soil Generator': Combining 'waste materials' to produce real life soils
- Organic framing as a set of technologies and practices
- 'Soil cleaning earthworms'
- 'Organic waste cleaner' (all contaminants)
- 'Soil health gene' (magic functionality)
- 'Perennial super plant mix' with a giant root system that removes all pollutants. An extracting machine is used for the pollutants to be recycled. Plant residues remain in the field (Carbon).
- Consumers
 - 'Soil footprint': Automated tool to show the real prices of products (indicators)
 - 'Soil health sensor' of food products (Consumers can use them at shops/markets)

Scenario 3 / Soil Health Community. Your community is entirely focused on soil health and very influential. What would they do and how would they operate?

Influencer groups:

- Bio-influencers in the private sector: Community of private companies developing crop protection solutions based on bio-products included in their business plans
- Community of Soil Life: Giving a voice to soil life
- Soil Culture and Soil Artistry
- Soil Social Status
- Soil economy
- Ocean community
- Urban composting community: Worm towers in each street! Farmers collect compost.
- Crop Land Suitable: Less nutrient use!
- Energy efficient sun-light-less community
- High-rise community for biodiversity and soil health: Smaller land footprint!
- Citizen awareness: Increase awareness and concern for soils to drive society and decision making. Focused on urban communities.

Advisor groups:

- Soil Doctors Without Borders: Call us for a solution!
- Provision of a full service to farmers, including soil information and advice on soil management
- Common Goods Model, supported by government
- Soil mapping: Biodiversity
- Sharing soil information for soil management: Like a weather forecast
- Genetically modified Worms Embrace Technology
- Urban Living Lab: Get Urban Living Lab started to recover degraded soils and train others to do the same.

Fig. 16: Results of the three vision journeys

6.5 Evaluation by participants

Participants were asked to provide feedback on the conference by means of a moderated online survey. On-line participants provided their feedback at the end of the morning session when the streaming was ended. The other participants provided their feedback at the end of the conference.

Here are some key insights from the evaluation:

- A general reluctance to join the survey was observed, as only 50% of the participants provided feedback. The reason for this reluctance is probably the fact that the surveys were conducted at the end of the streaming and at the end of the conference when participants were tired and ready to leave.
- With regard to the geographical distribution it can be noted that a few European countries were not reached, in particular small countries and several eastern European countries (see also chapter 3).
- Agriculture was the most represented land use.
- Engagement and interactive activities of the conference were highly appreciated.
- On-line participants did not enjoy the conference as much as in-situ participants, since they had less opportunities to engage.

7 RESSOURCES

Personal resources for conference planning were as follows

- conference manager: 28 working days
- 10 meetings of the conference planning team each 1 hour: approximately 5 working days in total.

External costs were as follows:

Table 2: External costs of SMS final conference

Item	Costs
meeting venue & catering	13 335 €
technology package, including streaming	5 010 €
graphic recording	1 680 €
travel costs	1 365 €

8 COMMUNICATION & DISSEMINATION

8.1 Before the conference

Conference invitations were sent to a recipient list with more than 7 000 addresses (see chapter 3).

Besides that, the conference was announced via the SMS website and via national channels through consortium partner organisations.

8.2 After the conference

A leaflet “Soil Mission Support – results” was produced to be widely disseminated at the conference and after the conference (see Fig. 18).

Fig. 18: SMS press text

The leaflet was disseminated via

- tweets from partner organisations
- the SMS website
- the SMS mailing list
- and backlinks at partner websites: <https://www.umweltbundesamt.at/news220927>.

Moreover, additional information is available on the SMS website:

- the recorded morning session of the conference
- the slides presented during the conference
- the illustrations from the graphic recording

9 CONCLUSIONS

The organisation of a large conference in times of COVID19 is very challenging.

With the SMS final conference, it was possible to reach a large audience from different sectors and all over Europe.

A variety of interactive tools were used, in order to maximise the engagement with the audience; i.e. a line up exercise, a vision journey, graphic recording, ample space for questions and answers.

It was possible to communicate and discuss complex topics; i.e. the soil mission, soil health, soil health objectives and the concept of soil Living Labs and Lighthouses.

Engagement of participants worked very well for those, who participated “face to face” and we received very positive feedback. It was however, not possible to provide the same level of engagement to the on-line participants.

A cause of concern was the “no show” attitude of registered participants, as 44% of registered participants did not show up, mostly unexcused. This was particularly unfortunate, since the number of participants was limited and we had to turn down registrations from other interested people. A recommendation for conference organisers is therefore to demand a small conference fee, in order to achieve a higher reliability.

10 ANNEX

10.1 Conference minutes

Minutes of the SMS final conference: A Soil Deal for Europe – European R&I Conference 27-09-2022 – Brussels

The Soil Mission Support (SMS) project supported the Horizon Europe Mission ‘A Soil Deal for Europe’, the European Green Deal, and contributed to the UN Sustainable Development Goals through improving the coordination of research and innovation (R&I) on sustainable soil and land management and bringing forward the promising Mission concept of Living Labs and Lighthouses. During the SMS final conference in Brussels, Belgium, the results of the SMS project were shared and discussed with a broad audience from the EC, related projects and the broader public.

Participants: 110 in total

17 members of the SMS consortium participated

54 external participants attended the venue

39 participants attended the conference online (morning session only)

Note takers:

Gerald Jan Ellen (Morning session)

Laura Nouges (Afternoon session)

Opening (9:00 – 9:45)

Johannes Bender (SMS) welcomed the audience and the speakers and introduced the agenda for the day.

Neville Reeve – Principal Advisor for missions; *DG Research and Innovation*: Introduced the Missions of Horizon Europe. The Mission concept should inspire people and provide fix points for progress and success. We need Missions for tackling mayor societal challenges and make sure that we work closely together towards specific goals. The Missions want to engage citizens for important social innovations in support of the priorities of the European Commission. The new Missions introduced strategic programming of research to develop a new pathway for impact, based on input, output and finally impact. The Missions should provide a link to citizens, be bottom up, cross sectorial, clearer on the impact we want to have (e.g. through defining indicators) and create inspirational value. They should be ambitious but also realistic and with specific deadlines. In 2023, there will be a review on what does a mission approach require (OECD is also working on this).

Orsolya Frizon Somogyi – Deputy head of unit research and innovation (F2), *DG for Agriculture and Rural Development*: Introduced the Horizon Europe Mission ‘A Soil Deal for Europe’. Soil health is a new topic for society and impacts on soils work differently than we address them right now. For the Mission, it is important to interact with actors and adapt the process where necessary. Since it is a longterm progress, there will be time to ‘listen’ and adapt. In addition, interactions between different actors need to be stressed and addressed (e.g. related to urbanisation or contamination of military installations). The overall Mission Objective is to make lands cleaner by 2030.

Question: How can the Soil Mission deal with the impact of energy and the war in Ukraine?

Answer: Yes, we are working on this; the Missions should consider the situation that we are in. For example the contaminations resulting from the situation in the Ukraine.

Results of the Soil Mission Support project (9:45 – 10:30)

Multiple SMS partners present the SMS results during an interview on stage (interviewer: *Saskia Keestra*, SMS). The Soil Mission Support (SMS) project results support the Horizon Europe Mission ‘A Soil Deal for Europe’ through improving the coordination of research and innovation on sustainable soil and land management. To ensure functional cross sectorial communication, SMS developed an ontology for sustainable soil and land management to promote a common language. The Soil Mission uses LLs & LHs as a central concept to be able to promote the transition towards healthy soils. SMS, together with the Soil Mission Board and other projects, developed criteria and success factors for soil health LLs. Candidates for LLs & LHs have been gathered throughout Europe and they have been enclosed in an interactive map.

A gap analysis was conducted to get an overview of existing R&I knowledge and stakeholders’ needs for a successful transition towards sustainable soil and land management. Major knowledge gaps address socio-economic questions, including socio-economic innovation (e.g. marketing and finance schemes), governance and policies conducive to sustainable management, raising awareness and general education. Further, many basic definitions are yet insufficient for practical implementation; e.g. what is soil health, degraded soil, or a global footprint on soils? Similarly, we need easy measurable indicators and respective threshold values to monitor changes and to develop legal frameworks, guidelines, and decision support tools. The SMS R&I Roadmap for sustainable soil and land management is a strategic document outlining actions and pathways to address R&I needs from different soil related stakeholders and sectors. It is developed iteratively through a stakeholder inclusive co-creation process. The Roadmap helps to guide and inform future research and policy agendas and to meet the Soil Mission objectives by 2050. It summarizes key findings of the SMS and proposes concrete actions to address R&I gaps with respect to achieving the Soil Mission objectives.

Finally, a knowledge platform is designed around the Mission goal to “establish 100 living labs and lighthouses to lead the transition towards healthy soils by 2030”. A web-display and an information package for LLs & LHs was produced, including a general explanation, an interactive map (see above), products from LLs & LHs, and a short movie. As the concept of LLs & LHs is rather new, the whole web-display for LLs & LHs is an evolving concept. This work will be transferred to the European Commission’s Joint Research Centre (JRC) soil platform and continued after the end of the SMS.

Towards Soil Health Living Labs and Lighthouses (10:30 – 11:20)

Paola-Alejandra Eulalio – DG for Agriculture and Rural Development: Presented the Soil Missions goal of establishing 100 soil health Living Labs by 2030. She presented the Soil Mission's definitions of Living Labs and Lighthouses (LLs&LHs) and the gradual development plan for a LL network covering all soil and land uses across Europe within and beyond the duration of the Soil Mission.

Marta De Los Rios White – European Network of Living Labs: Presented the ENOLL and their perspective on LLs and how they can support the Soil Mission. Their major focus lies on joint value co-production, prototyping and testing and scaling up. Further, she presented the ENOLL LL landscape and its structure. To specify, she presented some existing LLs and their activities. ENOLL offers LL quality assessment including certification and labelling, capacity building for establishing and improving LLs, and action oriented task forces and working groups for hot topics.

Juanita Devis – Amsterdam Institute for Advanced Metropolitan Solutions: Presented the way how AMS LLs work and reflected how they look like in different projects. LLs tackling urban problems need to address relevant problems with a transdisciplinary and co-creational approach that leads to an actual transformation. To specify, she presented different urban LLs and their approaches. Further, she presented the organizational approach of AMS for implementing successful LL projects.

Short round of questions from the audience:

- **Question:** We are organising a network of companies working on innovations within sectors rather than regions, but as we hear the definitions for LLs, we assume that this is not a LL, is it?
- **Answer:** It is always about the added value to the EU and reaching the Soil Mission. That is the most important criteria. But LLs are also about up scaling and sharing knowledge and ideas, which may differ from the work of companies.
- **Question:** how will LLs address the Mission objective of no-net-soil sealing?
- **Answer:** This is also a challenge that was pointed out in the SMS deliverable 3.3. LLs provide a safe and controlled environment for co-innovation and small scale testing, which then can be up scaled.

Panel discussion: Joining forces for achieving the soil mission (11:40 – 12:50)

Host: *Katharina Helming*, SMS, ZALF

Panellists:

- **Claudia Olazabal** – Head of unit of the Land Use & Management; DG for the Environment
- **Orsolya Frizon Somogyi** - Deputy head of unit research and innovation; DG for Agriculture and Rural Development
- **Horst Herzog** – Chairman of the Network for Industrially Coordinated Sustainable Land Management in Europe (NICOLE)
- **Liisa Pietola** – Leading specialist in the Finnish Innovation Fund, Sitra, and member of the Soil Mission Board

The Soil Mission aims at real impact. It is the start of a process that aims to engage multiple sectors to do their own part for healthy soils. Hence, the most crucial part of the Soil Mission is soil literacy to make people aware of soil related benefits and problems. While the Soil Mission covers a broad spectrum of soil sustainability issues, it does not claim to cover all related topics. Instead, it leaves room for other related activities and tries to leverage supportive member state financed initiatives.

From a political perspective, it is important to link The Soil Mission with the Green Deal, the Biodiversity Strategy and the Soil Strategy to create synergies. Therefore, the panel discussed the planned impact of the Soil Mission and its relation to the Soil Health Law and the Green Deal. Further, the CAP plays an important role and the private sector needs to agree that soil health is an economic goal.

Sustainable management always creates immediate cost, while benefits may take longer time to come through. Further, some actors are affected directly by reduced soil quality and other only indirectly. Therefore, economic issues are an important barrier for sustainable soil use. We need to evolve towards a human long-term cooperation with soils where we highlight ecosystem services and their monetary and non-monetary values. Pricing of ecosystem services was identified as an important task for this.

Regular and broad monitoring is needed to evaluate effects on soils, to evaluate changes of ecosystem services and to identify whether changes of actions deliver the desired outcomes. Thus, improved knowledge through monitoring allows us to be “*fair with nature and soil managers*” and to account for real prices and rewards. However, currently we are not fit for monetisation of ecosystem services, since economic evidence for soils is too scarce. Nonetheless, a general change of attitude can be observed towards a recognition of soils as a resource that requires sustainable management.

With monitoring being a key objective for progress, it is important to build upon existing monitoring initiatives and policies through connecting them in a meaningful way. However, quality of monitoring needs to be improved, time and space dynamics need to be considered, more pedo-climatic zones and (non-mainstream) management practices need to be covered, and societal and economic impacts need to be included. We need to overcome the mere monitoring of functions, but develop towards a monitoring of values. Finally, all soil related actions from indicators over monitoring to policies and actions are evolving concepts that change over time and with increasing knowledge and awareness. Therefore, continuous updating is required.

For informed decision-making, the concept of ‘soil health’ was discussed. Soil health is to a great extent a political term. In the Mission implementation plan, soil health is defined as ‘the continued capacity of soils to support ecosystem services’. But, the question of balancing costs and benefits is a key political (and societal) question for the Mission. However, this is also driven by increased demands

for change and improvement from the society. Hence, it is important that many people take ownership of the Soil Mission and “*join this journey*” towards sustainable soil and land management.

The future of European landscapes – Interactive exercise – vision journey (13:50 – 15:20)

The session started with a warm-up exercise where participants should position themselves on a fictive line in the room where one end represents that they think the Soil Mission will be fully implemented within the set time frame and the opposite end represents that they think the Soil Mission won't be successful at all. Most people positioned themselves in the middle with some more negative and some more positive people. As problems for the implementation for the Soil Mission, people stated the low awareness of people on the topic and the ambitious objectives of the mission that may be hard to fully achieve.

After the warm-up, the audience was randomly split into three overarching theme groups with the task to create an imaginary action to positively influence sustainable soil and land management. Within the theme groups, they were separated into groups with 4-6 members. To elaborate solution show they could best influence a sustainable development.

The first theme group represented a considerable ‘Individual’ with sustainable lifestyle and values and a profession that enables or promotes healthy soils (e.g. a school teacher, healthy soil blogger, minister, rock star, etc.). The second theme group should develop a ‘Technology’ that will be a real game changer for sustainable soil and land management (e.g. a land degradation alert system, large-scale soil regeneration machine, etc.). The third theme group should represent a trusted ‘Community’ that cares about healthy soils and creates the one group that will be the real game changer (e.g. land recycling pressure group, soil farmers’ union, etc.).

The ‘Individual’ groups presented themselves as a part time soil policy entrepreneur and sustainable food retailer, an ambitious biology teacher, a dictator that aims to implement sustainable soil management, an astronaut that provides another view on the earth, hobby farmers who do citizen science, networking and outreach, an artist that merges art with soil, or an architect who focuses on sustainable architecture.

The ‘Technology’ group invented a super plant that removes soil pollutants, an early warning system where earth worms inform us about the status of the soil health, an automatic tool that shows the real price of products, a soil health gene that can be incorporated into any plant and a hovercraft that destroys all pollutants in the soil.

The ‘Community’ group imagined itself as influencers of the private sector to lead the healthy soil transition, community of “Soil Doctors” without borders, Ministers for soil health, a community that focuses on soil appreciation, or a soil cult community in which soil is holy and you cannot harm it.

In summary, the participants covered both top down and bottom up approaches and included all sectors from policy, society, cultural, environment and economy.

European projects on soil (15:45 – 16:20)

Claire Chenu – INRAE: The EJP soil project

Claire presented the EJP Soil project that represents 24 countries, 26 partners and 45 institutes all over Europe. Through coordinated knowledge development, knowledge sharing and transfer, knowledge harmonization, organization and storage, and knowledge application, EJP Soil aims to align soil related agricultural research at EU scale and to make farmers stewards of land and soil resources that aim to adapt to and contribute to mitigate climate change. Due to the topic overlap, EJP Soil is a large contributor to achieving the objectives of the EU Soil Mission.

Audience Question: Which results from the SMS project will you take with you in EJP Soil?

Claire: Something that came out during the interaction with SMS is that each project (also others than SMS) wants to setup a knowledge sharing platform. However, what we see is that at the end of the project duration, the platforms disappear. There is therefore a need for coordination between the different projects and platforms.

Margrethe Balling Høstgaard – Aarhus University: the PREPSOIL project 2022-2025: Preparing for the 'Soil Deal for Europe' Mission

Margarethe presented the PREPSOIL project which takes over the work of the SMS to prepare the ground for the EU Mission 'Soil Deal for Europe', to further build capacities for stakeholder engagement, outreach and knowledge exchange. With multiple objectives, the project aims to support the Soil Mission objectives, further map knowledge needs for sustainable management, extend on the work on living labs (LL) and lighthouses (LH), extend awareness and exchange on sustainable soil and land management, harmonise and standardise soil monitoring and data collection across the EU, and build upon the work of the EJP Soil project.

Audience Question: Which part of the PREPSOIL project are you most excited about?

Margarthe: I'm looking forward to see which living labs will be established during our project time, but also to have a clear (and final) definition for LL and LH. In the coming months, there will be a crucial acceleration in the setting up of LL and LH. Before we start working towards the mission goal of establishing 100 LL and LH, we really need to have a final and clear definition of what they are and across which regions they spread.

Reflections on the workshop and closing (16:20 – 16:30)

Katharina summarized the results and experiences of the SMS Final Conference and closed the event.